

Cool Pavement Primer: A Guide to Reflective Pavement Solutions

2025

About The Smart Surfaces Coalition

The Smart Surfaces Coalition is a 501(c)(3) non-profit organization made up of more than 40 leading national and international organizations with a shared commitment to creating cooler, healthier, and more resilient cities by cost-effectively reducing the impacts of extreme urban heat and flooding. Smart Surfaces—reflective, porous, and green urban surfaces along with trees and solar PV—can cut peak summer temperatures by 5°F or more, decrease flood risk, slow climate change, and improve public health, with the greatest improvements in low-income neighborhoods and communities of color.

The Cool Pavement Primer was developed by the Smart Surfaces Coalition (SSC) to support cities and stakeholders in advancing heat-mitigating pavement solutions. To learn more about cool pavements, join the [Cool Roadways Partnership](#) (CRP) to participate in quarterly Zoom sessions with transportation officials, city engineers, sustainability managers, pavement researchers, and related organizations learning from active cool pavement projects and programs. For guidance on measures that support the implementation of cool pavement and other Smart Surfaces, visit SSC's best practice resources at [SmartSurfacesPolicy.org](#).

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1. An Introduction to Cool Pavement

Urban areas can be made cooler by deploying Smart Surfaces—reflective, porous, and green infrastructure such as cool roofs and walls, trees and rain gardens, and cool or permeable pavements. Cool pavement describes paving materials with a higher solar reflectance than conventional asphalt. These technologies reduce roadway heat absorption, serving as both an urban heat mitigation strategy and a pavement preservation treatment. This primer provides an overview of cool paving technologies and offers implementation guidance for local and regional governments.

Land cover mapping of 10 U.S. cities participating in the [Cities for Smart Surfaces](#) program estimates that paved surfaces cover a quarter to nearly half of city land area on average ([WRI](#)). New asphalt roads and parking lots absorb up to 95% of solar radiation and re-emit it as heat, contributing to the urban heat island effect and resulting in hotter cities during both day and night ([LBNL](#)). Excess heat increases energy demand, degrades air quality, and elevates the risk of heat-related illnesses and mortality. With more than half of the global population living in urban areas amid intensifying heat waves, cities urgently need effective heat mitigation strategies to safeguard public health, maintain public infrastructure, and enhance resilience.

Cool pavement technologies deployed in cities across Arizona, California, Texas, and the Carolinas, among others, have demonstrated measurable reductions in surface and air temperatures. During the hottest times of day, treated cool pavements remain 12-16 °F cooler than untreated asphalt ([Middel et al., 2024](#); [Taha, 2024](#)). Because the surface reflects heat rather than retaining it, cool pavement helps urban areas cool off quickly after sundown, reducing dangerous nighttime temperature highs. A study of community-wide cool pavement application in a Los Angeles neighborhood found average air temperature reductions of 2.1 °F during sunny days and 0.5 °F during summer nights. Air temperatures decreased by up to 3.5 °F during a recorded heatwave ([Taha, 2024](#)). In addition to alleviating the urban heat island effect, lower pavement temperatures extend the lifespan of roadways and parking lots, thereby reducing long-term road maintenance costs ([Pomerantz et al., 2000a](#)). When deployed under appropriate use cases, cool pavement can generate additional co-benefits, such as lower building energy consumption ([AzariJafari et al., 2021](#)) and improved traffic safety ([Schwartz, 2022](#)).

The key properties that determine the “coolness” of a material are **solar reflectance (SR)** and **thermal emittance (TE)**. Both are measured on a scale of 0 to 1, with 1 equating to 100% reflectance or emittance. The **Solar Reflectance Index (SRI)** is a calculated metric that combines SR and TE into a single value typically ranging from 0 to 100, and sometimes over 100 for highly reflective materials. Increasing these properties in pavements or utilizing photocatalytic materials that convert sunlight into chemical rather than thermal energy can lower surface, subsurface, and surrounding air temperatures.

Benefits of Cool Pavement

Cool pavements provide a range of benefits through their ability to:

- Mitigate urban heat island (UHI) effects and enhance thermal comfort for pedestrians and residents.
 - Reduce energy use and associated greenhouse gas emissions by lowering air temperatures.
 - Extend road lifespan and delay costly maintenance treatments by protecting against ultraviolet (UV) rays, extreme temperatures, and water penetration.
 - Reduce irrigation demands in arid climates by moderating air temperatures ([Middel et al., 2024](#)).
- Improve air quality by curbing smog formation from lower ambient temperatures ([U.S. EPA, 2012](#)).
 - Protect aquatic life by reducing the temperature of stormwater runoff ([U.S. EPA, 2012](#)).
 - Reflect solar radiation back into space, helping to restore the Earth’s energy balance.
 - Improve traffic safety by using vibrant colors for road markings, special-use lanes, crosswalks, and intersections ([Schwartz, 2022](#))
 - Improve nighttime visibility from increased light reflection, potentially reducing street lighting needs ([Pomerantz et al., 2000a](#); Stark, 1986).

- Break down vehicular pollutants, including nitrogen oxides (NO_x), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), microplastics, and carbon dioxide (CO₂), into harmless byproducts when pavement treatments contain catalytically active titanium dioxide (TiO₂) ([Li et al., 2023](#)).

Cool Pavement in Green Building Standards

Green building rating systems provide frameworks and certifications for sustainable and resilient sites and infrastructure. Multiple rating programs recognize and award credits for cool pavement as a heat mitigation strategy. The Leadership in Energy & Environmental Design (LEED) and the Sustainable SITES Initiative rating systems offer a Heat Island Reduction Credit for projects using paving materials with a three-year aged solar reflectance (SR) value of at least 0.28. When aged ratings are unavailable, materials with an initial SR of at least 0.33 qualify for the credit ([USGBC](#)).

Cool pavement implementation may also contribute to a handful of credits through the Envision rating system developed by the Institute for Sustainable Infrastructure. For instance, the CR0.0 credit recognizes projects that address additional aspects of sustainability, such as managing urban heat through Solar Reflectance Index (SRI) requirements for hardscape ([ISI](#)). Cool pavement may earn additional Envision credits for enhancing public health and safety, reducing operational energy consumption, maximizing resilience, and improving community quality of life. Check the [Smart Surfaces Policy Tracker](#) for a forthcoming resource detailing Smart Surface alignment with infrastructure rating programs.

Moving to Standardization

The growing interest in cool pavement as a heat-mitigation strategy has underscored the need for systematic evaluations to provide objective, scientific information on the cooling potential of different materials.

In 2023, the Cool Roof Rating Council (CRRC) began to explore the development of a rating program for pavement materials. The CRRC's existing rating programs for roofing and exterior wall products provide radiative property data to support decisions about procurement, installation, compliance, and enforcement of cool surfaces. In an effort to expand CRRC program offerings, the Board of Directors formed the [Pavement Ratings Steering Committee](#) to explore and evaluate the program procedures, requirements, and feasibility of a pavement material rating program. A CRRC Pavement Rating Program would fill the gap of a third-party rating system for compliance with LEED and other green building programs and assist in identifying products for cool pavement initiatives.

While a CRRC rating program would aim to provide data on initial radiative properties and simulated aging effects, other pavement material properties will be outside the program's purview. Evaluations by other parties could assess photocatalytic smog-reducing properties, long-term durability under varied use cases, and the impact of other road treatments – such as snowplows, road salt, and de-icing agents. Federal and state transportation departments can play a pivotal role in advancing cutting-edge, heat-mitigating pavement technologies by investing in research and fostering product innovation to maximize benefits and mitigate any unintended consequences.

2. Overview of Cool Pavement Technologies

Cool pavement technologies are formulated using a variety of materials, each offering varied properties and use cases. The following section introduces various cool pavement technology types, including product costs, service life, solar reflectance, and additional benefits based on a review of published materials and industry guidance.

Cool pavement products are typically applied directly to clean, prepared pavement via spray, squeegee, or roller, similar to conventional seal coats. Some products can be used on concrete, but in terms of their urban heat reduction potential, cool pavements are most impactful on dark asphalt. Cool pavement provides more notable benefits when applied across entire neighborhoods or cities. Larger, contiguous applications maximize the reflection of solar energy in a given area, mitigating urban heat islands far more efficiently than isolated installations. A comprehensive application also minimizes the occurrence of tire tracks from adjacent asphalt streets, which can degrade the high solar reflectance of cool pavement. Cool pavement generally does not require maintenance; however, occasional street sweeping to remove dirt and debris can help maintain high solar reflectance.

Polymer Modified Concrete/Composite Overlays

Image Credits: Endurablend

Road surface coatings made with combinations of polymer modifiers, aggregates, additives, and cement cap pavement with a durable, reflective layer that repairs existing deterioration and protects surfaces from cracking and spalling. Typically applied with squeegees or spray-applied by certified installers.

Installed Cost: \$2-4/ft² for roadways; \$5-10/ft² for bike lanes, \$10-12/ft² for large decorative areas, and \$16-20/ft² for decorative crosswalks.

Lifespan: 8-10 years on residential roads, 5 years on highways.

Initial Solar Reflectance: 0.30-0.40+, depending on color

Potential Uses: Virtually no limitations on road or traffic types. Can be

applied to asphalt and concrete in most conditions for repair and preservation, decorative purposes, lane marking, traffic calming, and safety surfacing.

Notes: High durability, unaffected by deicing chemicals, snowplows, and petroleum products, available in multiple colors. One manufacturer offers a 3-year warranty on roadways with average annual daily traffic up to 50,000.

CASE STUDY: The City of Dallas used OXCON's HP Surfacer as a cost-effective and low-carbon alternative to standard tear-out and replacement of 6.1 miles of aging concrete roads. The overlay was spread between 2-3mm. Cost: The city has spent just over \$2 million on this project. Impact: Solar reflectance was measured to be ≥ 0.44 , with a thermal emittance of 0.90. Measured surface temperature reduction was up to 14°F compared to standard concrete.

Image Credits: Oxcon Systems

Photocatalytic Pavement Rejuvenators or Sealers

Image Credits: Pavement Technology, Inc.

Photocatalytic rejuvenators or sealers penetrate road surfaces with titanium dioxide nanoparticles to increase reflectivity, prevent aging, and remediate pollutants, including CO₂, NO_x, VOCs, and microplastics. Applied on roads in good condition in a single layer with a truck-mounted sprayer and dries clear.

Installed Cost: ~\$0.33-\$0.44/ft²

Lifespan: ~7 years to return to initial road condition. After 7 years, treated roads are slower to oxidize.

Initial Solar Reflectance Index (on asphalt): ≥ 39

Initial Solar Reflectance (on concrete): ≥ 0.35

Potential Uses: Suitable for virtually all road types and traffic volumes. Can be used on asphalt and concrete roads that are 1-3 years old and have had no previous coatings or seals.

CASE STUDY: In 2021, Charleston County Public Works piloted PlusTi as an alternative to Reclamite for its added environmental benefits, including heat-island reduction and improved air quality. Cost: \$21,000 per mile. Impact: Testing by Texas A&M found that PlusTi reduced vehicle NOx emissions by 39%, eliminated nearly all roadway microplastic debris from tire wear and brake pads, and is estimated to extend the life of the road by 5 years. The road surface was four times emissive as the untreated surface. As a result, Charleston County Council's [FY 25-27 Strategic Plan](#) includes a commitment to increase the alternative pavement preservation (e.g., use of Photocatalytic Rejuvenator) program by 5% annually on qualifying roads – the County is exceeding this annual deployment target.

Image Credits: [Charleston County Government](#)

Epoxy-Fortified Acrylic Seals

Image Credits: SSC (ii)

Water-based acrylic coating with reflective pigments, applied in two coats with a truck-mounted sprayer, brush, or roller.

Installed Cost: \$0.65-\$0.95/ft² for large road areas, up to \$7/ft² for decorative uses requiring manual application.

Lifespan: ~5 years

Initial Solar Reflectance: ≥ 0.33

Potential Uses: Residential roads, parking lots, and other low-traffic areas. Suitable for use on asphalt or concrete in good condition.

Notes: Colorful pigments can be added to enhance the visibility of special-use lanes and crosswalks.

CASE STUDY: In the [Pacoima neighborhood](#) of Los Angeles, CA, over 700,000 square feet of StreetBond cool pavement coatings were applied to dark

asphalt within a 10-block perimeter, including streets, a school playground, a street mural, a basketball court, and two parking lots. [12-month monitoring by Altostratus, Inc.](#) compared the treatment area to a control area. No specific cost info available.

Impact:

- Average daytime air temperature reductions of 2.1 °F and up to 3.5 °F during an extreme heat event. Average nighttime reductions of 0.5 °F.
- 25-50% reduction in the local census-tract urban heat island effect during temperature peaks, and 13-21% average reduction across a 24-hr period.
- Average daytime surface temperature reductions of 10 °F. Pavement warms up slower pre-solar noon and cools down faster post-solar noon.
- No negative thermal comfort impacts on average during the daytime on sunny days based on two standard industry metrics (MRT and PET).
- No increase of glare for drivers based on spectral analysis.

Image Credits: [Surface Optics](#)

¹ Solar Reflectance and Solar Reflectance Index values are likely under estimated. Accepted test methods capture only the amount of solar energy reflected from a surface. Photocatalytic materials absorb in the UV spectrum but convert that energy to chemical, rather than thermal energy. This makes these materials cooler than their reflectance values may indicate.

Reflective Asphalt Emulsion Sealcoat

Image Credits: [Cities Today](#)

Water-based asphalt emulsion sealcoats with reflective pigments increase reflectance in the visible and near-infrared range. Applied in two coats with a truck-mounted sprayer.

Product Cost: \$0.60-\$0.80/ft²

Lifespan: ~5 years, depending on local factors and traffic conditions.

Initial Solar Reflectance: ≥0.33

Potential Uses: Residential roads, parking lots, and other low-traffic areas. Only for use on asphalt in good condition.

Notes: Available in multiple shades to suit local preferences. Colorful pigments can be added to enhance the visibility of special-use lanes, crosswalks, etc.

Image Credits: [ASU, David Sailor](#)

CASE STUDY: In Phoenix, AZ, in Sept 2023, 63,000 sq. ft of parking lot at Desert Ridge Marketplace was resurfaced with CoolSeal, while the surrounding pavement was resurfaced with a conventional dark sealcoat.

Cost: Although project costs aren't specified, Phoenix has invested over \$12 million in its cool pavement program to date, covering 140 lane miles. Other projects estimate costs of \$0.67-\$1.60/ft².

Impact:

- Surface temperature reductions averaged 14 °F at 1 pm.
- Subsurface temperature was reduced by 3.6 °F to 7 °F in mid-afternoon hours, which could improve pavement lifespan due to less thermal cycling.
- Afternoon air temperatures at pedestrian height were reduced by ~1.0 °F in summer.
- Cooling at a height of 10 ft throughout the year was in the range of 0.5 °F to 1.0 °F in the evening hours and 0.3 °F to 0.5 °F during the day.
- ASU estimates that widespread deployment of cool pavement could yield City of Phoenix households 28M gallons of reduced residential water use per summer month and \$10-20M in annual energy savings ([Middel et al., 2024](#)).

Asphalt Shot Blasting or Diamond Grinding

Abrasion techniques can be used to remove the top millimeters of dark bitumen, increasing albedo without installing a new surface or coating, thereby reducing costs, disruption, and environmental impact.

Image Credits: [Jesse Costa/WBUR](#)

Cost: \$0.30-\$0.46/ft²

Lifespan: Maintains higher reflectance for the life of the road.

Initial Solar Reflectance Index: 0.18-0.24+, depending on aggregate.

Uses: Blast treatment should occur around 5 weeks after pavement application to provide time for sufficient setting of the pavement.

Notes: Can improve or restore skid resistance.

CASE STUDY: As part of a [Cool Block](#) initiative in the City of Chelsea, MA, regional asphalt manufacturer Holcim produced a lighter aggregate mix to

modify the albedo of hot mix asphalt. Shot blasting with Blastrac systems removed the surficial bitumen, revealing a lighter gray pavement. **Cost:** The aggregate mix and shot blasting cost approximately \$55,000 for a 1.5-inch mill and overlay with light-colored aggregate on Willow Street.

Cool Pavement Materials Summary Table

Technology Type	Initial SR	Cost	Lifespan on Residential Streets	Uses & Installation Guidance
Polymer Modified Concrete Overlays	0.30 - 0.40+	\$2-4/ft ² for large road areas, up to \$20/ft ² for decorative use	~8-10 years	Suitable for virtually all traffic volumes and road conditions. Can be used to repair asphalt or concrete in poor condition, or to preserve pavement in good condition.
Photocatalytic Pavement Rejuvenators	≥0.35	\$0.33-\$0.44/ft ²	~7 years	Suitable for virtually all traffic volumes. Can be used on asphalt or concrete in good condition (1-3 years old) with no previous coatings or seals.
Epoxy-Fortified Acrylic Seals	≥0.33	\$0.65-\$0.95/ft ² for large road areas, up to \$7/ft ² for decorative use	~5 years	Residential roads, parking lots, and other low-traffic areas. Suitable for use on asphalt or concrete in good condition.
Reflective Asphalt Emulsion Sealcoat	≥0.33	\$0.60-\$0.80/ft ²	~5 years	Residential roads, parking lots, and other low-traffic areas. Suitable for use on asphalt in good condition. Asphalt should cure for ≥180 days before application.
Asphalt Shot Blasting	0.18 - 0.24+	\$0.30-\$0.46/ft ²	15+ years	Blast treatment should occur 4-5-weeks after pavement installation to provide sufficient time for setting of pavement.

Additional Strategies

Concrete additives and light-colored aggregates incorporate reflectivity directly into pavement mixes, ensuring long-lasting reflectivity benefits in high-traffic areas. Concrete admixtures containing white cement, titanium dioxide, or other pigments can increase concrete's solar reflectance to 0.40 or higher. Pigments are typically introduced during the mixing process to ensure a uniform appearance. Aggregates produced from light-colored rocks, including anorthosite, quartz, limestone, and white labradorite, have natural reflective properties. These aggregates should be combined with transparent or light-colored binders to avoid altering the color of aggregates and achieve an initial solar reflectance of 0.33 or greater. Other conventional paving materials, such as resin-based methyl methacrylate (MMA) traffic paints, are available in a variety of solar-reflective colors with an initial solar reflectance of 0.33 or greater. Bold color options and high durability make MMA traffic paints a popular choice for crosswalks and traffic marking, as well as bus, bike, and other specialty-use lanes. MMA traffic paints are typically applied with squeegees, walk-behind equipment, or trucks.

Cool Pavement Benefit-Cost Analysis

Cool pavement costs depend on several factors, including the technology type and installation method, as well as project size and location. Most cool pavement technologies can be used in place of conventional materials, either at a comparable price point or with a slight cost premium that is typically offset by increased road durability and additional community benefits. When considering cool pavement strategies, it is important to account for additional environmental and maintenance benefits to generate a comprehensive economic assessment. Cool pavement materials protect roadways from deterioration caused by oxidation, moisture, and thermal cycling, reducing overall

maintenance cadence and lifecycle costs. Furthermore, cool pavement materials can be recycled and repurposed. Research conducted by Arizona State University found no negative impacts of using millings from cool-coated asphalt in reclaimed asphalt pavement ([Middel et al., 2024](#)). Lifecycle cost assessments and benefit-cost analyses can help evaluate the true costs of cool pavement materials compared with conventional maintenance treatments such as slurry seals, fog seals, and microsurfacing.

The [Smart Surfaces Coalition](#) generates detailed, location-specific benefit-cost analyses to evaluate the impact of Smart Surface implementation. As of 2025, analysis of the 10 U.S. [Cities for Smart Surfaces](#) shows an average positive net present value of \$59,000/lane mile when cool pavement is applied to 25% of city road and parking lots over a 15-year period, with benefits and costs observed for 35 years. Cool pavement installation costs are based on a mid range cost of \$0.78/ft². A 25% implementation scenario is estimated to reduce peak citywide air temperatures by 0.21 °F on average, and avoid 219,000 metric tons of CO₂ equivalent emissions from negative radiative forcing and electricity demand reduction.

Impact	10-City Average
<i>Avoided CO2e emissions (MTCO2e)</i>	-219,100
Global Cooling / Negative Radiative Forcing	-217,100
Electricity demand reduction	-2,000
<i>Smart Surface Costs</i>	-\$299,126,000
First Cost Premium	-\$69,679,000
Additional Replacements	-\$229,447,000
<i>Smart Surface Benefits</i>	\$477,346,000
Indirect Energy Savings	\$258,000
Avoided Air Pollution (Indirect Energy Savings)	\$36,000
Reduced Attributable Heat Related Mortality	\$55,147,000
Avoided Conventional Surface Costs	\$232,169,000
Surface Life Extension	\$189,736,000
<i>Net Present Value</i>	\$178,215,000
Benefit-Cost Ratio	1.7
Benefits per Lane Mile	\$148,000
NPV per Lane Mile	\$59,000

Temperature-related benefits from cool pavement implementation are modeled using high-resolution hourly micrometeorological simulations conducted by [Altostratus, Inc.](#) These simulations quantify the potential for ambient air temperature reductions from widespread deployment of cool pavement technologies across urban environments. For each city, Altostratus modeled an aggressive deployment scenario in which 100% of classified road and parking surfaces received cool pavement coatings. Below is an example output for the City of Phoenix, AZ, where the potential cooling effect from ambitious cool pavement deployment is up to 1.83 °F. Hourly model outputs were used to establish a regression model to quantify temperature-related benefits.

See Section 8 for key assumptions and methods used in the Smart Surfaces Benefit-Cost Analysis Tool (BCAT). Detailed BCAT results are currently available for metro areas participating in the [Cities for Smart Surfaces](#) program.

Reduction in Air Temperature from Cool Pavement Adoption

This map illustrates the potential cooling effect from widespread adoption of cool pavements on a hot summer afternoon – **August 9, 2020**. It shows the peak temperature reduction from an ambitious yet feasible citywide implementation scenario, modeled at a time of day when cooling benefits would be most impactful. Some temperature grids do not cover the full city boundary/area. Map is symbolized using a minimum-to-maximum raster stretch method based on equal intervals.

3. Cool Pavement Project Elements

Project Objectives

The goal of a cool pavement project or program is to increase the lifespan and durability of asphalt roads through proactive pavement maintenance while simultaneously mitigating urban heat, improving community health, and enhancing resilience. These benefits lead to substantial cost savings for municipalities. The following section outlines key considerations for a successful cool pavement project, from selecting appropriate sites and materials to engaging stakeholders and integrating cooling strategies city-wide.

Site Selection

Cool pavement is more effective at offsetting the localized urban heat island effect when applied comprehensively and contiguously throughout a neighborhood rather than in isolated segments. To maximize the heat-mitigation benefits of cool pavements, prioritize application on streets with limited opportunities to expand tree canopy and in areas experiencing extreme heat. The Pavement Condition Index (PCI) can further refine roadway selection, as cool pavement is best suited for asphalt streets less than three years old.

Geospatial tools such as the [Smart Surfaces Decision Support Tool](#) and the [Environmental Justice Screening and Mapping Tool \(EJScreen\)](#) can help identify target project areas. These tools overlay data on heat exposure, demographics, or existing infrastructure to prioritize sites for intervention. Considerations for selecting ideal sites for cool pavement may include:

1. Community input
2. Heat vulnerability and exposure
3. Areas with limited opportunities for increasing tree canopy
4. Wide, unshaded streets or narrow streets with suitable orientations
5. Air quality index
6. Pavement condition
7. Heat health data

Coupling cool pavement with street trees, rain gardens, permeable pavement, and other Smart Surfaces will result in optimal cooling and health outcomes. Cities can use enhanced community engagement strategies to introduce residents to cool pavement materials and their expected benefits, while listening to voiced concerns. Two-way engagement is vital to the success of a cool pavement project, especially when these new materials are introduced in historically marginalized communities.

Materials Selection

Material selection should primarily reflect the target area's traffic conditions and the project's end goals. The various cool pavement solutions offer a versatile toolkit, ranging from low-cost coatings for parking lots and low-traffic residential streets to durable treatments for bus lanes, arterials, and interstates.

Ultimately, an independent product testing and rating system is critical to assess the properties and suitable use cases of all cool pavement products. In the interim, performance-based procurement can help ensure the selection of top-performing, traffic-appropriate solutions.

First and foremost, selected products must meet road performance criteria – including appropriate friction coefficients for vehicle and pedestrian safety in wet and dry conditions – with the added benefit of higher solar reflectance. Performance-based procurement processes can help identify high-performing materials that meet durability, safety, and reflectivity standards. In addition to meeting technical specifications, lifecycle assessments can evaluate the broader environmental impact of materials, helping cities choose solutions with lower embodied carbon

See **Section 3** for suggested language and performance goals to include in a Request for Proposals (RFP) for pavement maintenance projects.

Stakeholder Partnerships

Cross-agency coordination, community outreach, and scientific monitoring are key aspects of a successful cool pavement project or program. Consider partnerships among the following stakeholder groups when designing such projects.

1. **Municipal Government Agencies:** Collaboration among public works, planning, parks, and transportation departments, public transit authorities, emergency response teams, and school districts can help streamline project implementation.
2. **Community-Based Organizations:** Trusted local organizations may conduct community outreach throughout the project to communicate anticipated benefits, answer questions, and address any concerns.
3. **Research Entities:** University research teams or local firms can conduct heat mapping to guide site selection and comprehensive data collection to assess the impact of cool pavement coatings.
4. **Local Artists:** Incorporating an artistic element, such as a crosswalk street mural, can enhance pedestrian safety while raising public awareness of heat mitigation strategies.

Public Engagement

Community education and outreach are vital to the success of a cool pavement pilot or program. Prior to implementation, residents should understand the project's objectives, anticipated benefits, and the materials being used. Messaging to residents should thoughtfully present cool pavement as a proven solution for heat risk-prone communities, rather than an experimental initiative.

While outreach efforts may involve upfront costs, these investments help ensure a smooth implementation process and build community support for heat resilience actions – ultimately contributing to project success. Municipalities may explore grant opportunities, public-private partnerships, and cost-sharing models to help offset expenses. Providing advance notice to affected residents, clear signage, and appropriate traffic controls during implementation can help minimize inconvenience and disruption. Gathering community feedback during the testing phase is equally important to ensure the project meets residents' needs and expectations. Examples of engagement strategies include:

1. **Educational Campaign:** Provide public information on the benefits of cool pavement, how it works, and what residents can expect before, during, and after installation. Aim to disseminate information through multiple channels, such as mailed materials, door-to-door canvassing, posts on a municipal website, and/or social media.
2. **Community Listening Sessions & Workshops:** With support from community-based organizations, introduce the project to residents, answer community questions, and address concerns. Gather community input on any artistic elements, such as a street mural.
3. **Coating Notification:** Prior to application, notifications to households affected by street closures will help residents navigate inconveniences and comply with traffic controls.
4. **Community Involvement Opportunities:** Volunteer days, student participation, artist collaborations, and local business involvement are all ways to enhance community strength and inclusion through cool pavement projects.
5. **Post-Application Evaluation:** Solicit feedback from residents to assess community satisfaction. Record temperature measurements and publish performance monitoring results for the community.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Project monitoring is key to understanding the effectiveness of cool pavement in each unique project context and microclimate. Consider establishing a research partnership with a local university or firm, or tracking performance internally. A research component will generate valuable data on the effectiveness of cool pavement in a local context.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Investing in research and data collection enables municipalities to make informed decisions and optimize future implementations to maximize financial, and environmental benefits. Data collection can help to justify public expenditures by demonstrating quantifiable benefits – such as lower surface and air temperatures, improved public health outcomes, and longer-lasting roadways – ensuring effective use of funding. Additionally, data can support future funding opportunities.

Cool pavement evaluation should aim to capture the following elements:

1. Control measurements of an adjacent, untreated area, whether in a before-and-after or side-by-side comparison (or preferably both, e.g., “difference-of-differences”). Test and reference areas should have similar characteristics, including weather conditions, tree cover, sun exposure, street orientation, sky-view factors, urban morphology, and pavement types.
2. Local weather data, including air temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed and direction at pedestrian height (2 meters above ground level).
3. Surface and subsurface temperatures.
4. Solar reflectance measured before, immediately after, and over time using a reflectometer or spectroradiometer.
5. Human experience (qualitative and/or quantitative) in pedestrian areas.
6. Financial impacts, such as reductions in long-term road maintenance costs.

A [2024 study by Taha](#) in the Pacoima neighborhood of Los Angeles contains descriptions and detailed methods for the above aspects and procedures. Additionally, Climate Resolve’s [Shine On Initiative](#) is developing a methodology for quantifying the global radiative forcing impact of cool surfaces in terms of reductions in carbon dioxide equivalent emissions.

City-Wide Integration of Cooling Strategies

Cool pavement technologies offer a scalable, cost-effective maintenance solution with significant urban cooling benefits. Municipalities such as Tucson and Phoenix, AZ, Los Angeles, CA, San Antonio, TX, Durham, NC, Charleston County, SC, and others have successfully integrated cool pavement into regular street maintenance programs following positive pilot project outcomes. To advance implementation, municipalities can also adopt ordinances requiring cool pavements for municipal streets and parking lots, or mandate their use on new private parking lots, for example.

The effectiveness of cool pavement programs are maximized when municipalities adopt a portfolio approach, customizing strategies to local needs. Just as cool roofs encompass a range of products suited to various roof types, cool pavement strategies should include a blend of technologies to address the diverse conditions of each road type and maximize benefits from deployment.

Furthermore, integrating cool pavements with urban tree canopies, cool roofs, and green infrastructure can deliver greater benefits for communities. Research indicates that cool pavements can enhance tree vitality by lowering root-zone temperatures, promoting larger canopies, and reducing tree mortality rates during extreme heat events ([Peluso et al., 2022](#)). These benefits make cool pavements an excellent complement to urban trees, which provide shade and amplify cooling effects. When combined with other Smart Surfaces – such as cool roofs, solar PV shade structures, permeable pavement, and green infrastructure – these solutions synergistically reduce urban heat, manage stormwater runoff, and strengthen urban resilience.

The effectiveness of cool pavement programs also hinges on comprehensive planning, strategic deployment, community involvement, and stakeholder collaboration. By prioritizing equity, leveraging partnerships, and fostering public involvement, municipalities can maximize the benefits of cool pavements and other Smart Surface solutions.

4. Suggested Language for Procurement

The following section offers sample language to assist municipalities in specifying cool pavement, including project justification, objectives, and relevant performance standards. **[Bracketed and colored items]** are placeholders that should be replaced with information appropriate to each jurisdiction. The language in this section may be useful to incorporate into an RFP or other procurement processes, but it may not address every local procurement rule or requirement. Before borrowing language from this section, it is important to confirm all locally applicable requirements.

Justification

Many urban areas across the globe, including **[Municipality Name]**, experience higher temperatures due to heat-absorbing infrastructure. This overheating, known as the urban heat island (UHI) effect, occurs when materials like black asphalt absorb solar energy, keeping temperatures elevated during day and night. Excess heat negatively impacts urban communities and the environment, leading to increased energy consumption, worsened air quality, and heightened risks of heat-related illnesses and mortality. These extreme heat conditions are further exacerbated by climate change.

Cool pavement is one of many strategies to mitigate heat caused by dark and impervious surfaces in the built environment. Cool pavement materials stay cooler than conventional pavement by reflecting more sunlight and efficiently emitting absorbed heat. Lower pavement temperatures also lead to a longer service life of roadways and parking lots ([Pomerantz et al., 2000](#)). Cool pavements are especially useful in addressing UHI effects in unshaded urban areas where tree planting or shade structures are not feasible. When applied at scale, cool pavements lower cooling demand, improve air quality, and reduce risk factors associated with adverse health impacts.

[Municipality Name], herein referred to as **[“City”]**, seeks written proposals from qualified vendors and installers for the application of cool pavement at locations specified by the City and in accordance with the requirements set forth in this document.

Project Overview

[Insert background here on pilots or programs that the Municipality has conducted to combat the UHI effect (e.g., cool pavement pilots, tree planting, permeable pavement, shade structures)]

[Add information on funding/financing types received or awarded (e.g., budget allocation, federal or state grant program funds)]

[List tools or data sources that the City will leverage for location selection, such as city-level geospatial datasets, local mobility plans, or regional planning tools. Other helpful tools may include the following:

- [Environmental Justice Screening and Mapping Tool \(EJScreen\)](#)
- [Smart Surfaces Coalition Decision Support Tool](#) (for cities in the 10 metro areas where this tool is currently available)
- [NIHHIS Heat & Health Tracker](#)

Project Objectives

The **City** is issuing this solicitation for the application of cool pavement to **[XX]** lane miles. The product must meet or exceed the requirements outlined in Table 1.

Contractor shall provide the following services:

- Provide **City**-approved notifications to all residents and businesses adjacent to the work area at least ten (10) business days in advance of work commencement date. Community notifications to include:
 - A brief description of the cool pavement product and the benefits it offers

- The location, date(s), and times of work
- Times when street will be inaccessible to the public, and when the street will be returned to service
- Contact number for questions
- Other information or instructions for the successful completion of the project
- Prepare the roadway surface as per the manufacturer's technical requirements to ensure proper bonding of coating to the roadway surface.
- Apply cool pavement coating on roadways at locations specified by the **City** and following the manufacturer's recommendations for the number of coats and drying intervals based on the pavement characteristics and atmospheric conditions at the time of application.
- Monitor the drying using on-site staff and notify the **City** when the coating is ready to receive traffic.
- Work within specific schedules for each neighborhood project as approved in advance by the **City**.
- Provide all necessary traffic controls for the safe application of the product, and coordinate with the **City** on parking signage and enforcement services.
- Ensure that services are provided in an appropriate manner that meets all applicable environmental protection requirements and health and safety laws. Contractor is solely responsible for ensuring that its staff are properly trained, dressed, and equipped to fully perform the services required.

Successful execution of the project consists of the ability to deliver the following:

- Contractor must ensure product availability for the successful completion of the project.
- Contractor must monitor the application, effectiveness, and wearability of the product.
- Contractor must provide reliable independent scientific data to support the effectiveness of the product in pavement maintenance and surface temperature reductions.

Please see **Table 1** for Cool Pavement Product Specifications.

Standard Tests & Performance Specifications

Material Property	Standard Test Method	Performance Goal
Solar Reflectance Index (Initial)	ASTM E1980	>30
Solar Reflectance (Initial)	ASTM E1918-06	>0.33
Friction	ASTM E965-15, ASTM E303-22, ASTM E274/ E274M-15 or ASTM E1911 (typically used by airports)	>65 (Wet) >35 (Dry)

5. Funding Sources

Implementing cool pavement projects requires an upfront investment, but materials and installation can be cost-competitive with other asphalt treatment technologies, such as slurry seals, on a first-cost basis. On a lifecycle basis, the reduced maintenance costs, public health benefits, and energy savings typically make these technologies cost-effective strategies for pavement maintenance and heat mitigation in cities. Federal funding programs listed below could support such projects. Municipalities may also leverage state grants, public-private partnerships, and municipal bonds to fund cool pavement projects. Check the [Smart Surfaces Policy Tracker](#) for a forthcoming resource detailing additional urban resilience finance strategies.

Funding applications can be strengthened by highlighting the measurable benefits of cool pavement. For example, the [Smart Surfaces Benefit-Cost Analysis Tool](#) (BCAT) quantifies the net present value of cool pavement implementation, weighing benefits against installation costs, maintenance expenses, frequency, and material service life. The BCAT calculates the impact of cool pavement on air quality, surface lifespan, energy use, greenhouse gas emissions, and global cooling, to make the case for investment.

Note: The landscape for federal funding opportunities has shifted under the current administration. While programs such as PROTECT and BRIC have been put on pause, the administration has rebranded the former DOT RAISE program into a new DOT BUILD program, and funding for cool pavement projects could be available under this path. It is possible that the administration will rebrand and re-release other programs, which could provide additional opportunities for cool pavements and other Smart Surface projects. The Smart Surfaces Coalition is continuing to monitor relevant federal funding opportunities.

Program	Description	Type	Eligible Entities
Safe Streets and Roads for All	Supports (1) the development of a comprehensive safety action plan that identifies the most significant roadway safety concerns and (2) the implementation of projects and strategies to address roadway safety issues.	Competitive, project-based	Political subdivisions of a state - counties, cities, towns, transit agencies, and other special districts, MPOs, Tribal Nations
Promoting Resilient Operations for Transformative, Efficient, and Cost-saving Transportation (PROTECT) Program	Supports the transformation of surface transportation systems to resilient hubs. Addresses at-risk roadway infrastructure and improved resilience to evacuation routes.	Competitive, project-based	States, Tribal Nations, local governments, MPOs, transit authorities
Building Resilient Infrastructure and Communities (BRIC)	Supports proactive investment in community resilience and risk reduction associated with natural disasters.	Competitive, project-based through state selection	States, Tribal Nations, local and territorial governments
Better Utilizing Infrastructure to Leverage Development (BUILD) Grant Program	Supports the planning and/or construction of surface transportation infrastructure.	Competitive, project-based	States, Tribal Nations, local and territorial governments, transit authorities, and more
Surface Transportation Block Grant	Supports the preservation and improvement of roadway conditions & performance on any public road, pedestrian and bicycle infrastructure, and transit capital project.	Formula	Cities and local governments

6. Frequently Asked Questions

Q: Is cool pavement a viable option in cold-weather climates?

A: While cool pavements may not provide as significant temperature reductions in colder climates compared to warmer regions, they still offer benefits such as summer temperature reductions, reduced freeze-thaw cycles, enhanced durability and longevity – and, in the case of the photocatalytic technologies, reduced air pollution, carbon dioxide sequestration, and microplastics mitigation. Many cool pavement products, such as epoxy-fortified acrylics and cement polymer materials, are formulated using technologies that have been used for decades in roadway preservation in both hot and cold climate zones. These technologies are designed to protect pavement from common damage associated with UV rays, snow, salt, fuel, and chemicals. It is important to note that salt and snowplows increase pavement abrasion and could cause surface-coating technologies to wear off faster, depending on the material type (some cool pavement coatings infuse into the pavement structure, while others are surface layers). As a result, manufacturers may recommend increasing the thickness of the applied material in colder climates to achieve similar material lifespans.

Q: Are cool pavement materials more expensive than traditional pavement preservation treatments?

A: This depends on the technology and which conventional asphalt maintenance material is used for the comparison. Some cool pavement materials are available at a lower or comparable cost to conventional treatments. Other cool pavement materials may have a higher upfront cost than conventional asphalt sealants, but yield long-term savings through reduced maintenance costs and lower energy consumption, for example. Cool pavement materials slow deterioration caused by oxidation, moisture, and thermal cycling, significantly delaying the need for expensive, intensive maintenance options such as mill and repave.

Q: Does cool pavement make pedestrians hotter?

A. Some studies report thermal comfort improvements across multiple thermal comfort metrics, in addition to a reduction in the local urban heat island effect, as a result of cool pavement ([Donthu et al. 2024](#), [Taha 2024](#)). Other studies report moderate increases in mean radiant temperature (MRT) when measured in the center of a street that has received cool pavement coating. However, when measured from an adjacent sidewalk, no significant difference in MRT was recorded between asphalt and cool paved roads ([Schneider et al., 2023](#)). Furthermore, cool pavement does not increase a pedestrian's UV exposure or risk of sunburn ([Middel et al., 2024](#)). Ultimately, additional research is needed to fully understand the impact of cool pavement on pedestrians. Studies to date have utilized sensors, but not human subjects. It is possible that an increase in shortwave radiation or MRT might be mitigated or negated by decreased pavement temperature and longwave radiation. Additionally, comprehensive treatment of all roads in an area would reduce ambient air temperatures, most notably during heat waves.

Q: How will cool pavement affect drivers?

A. Performance-based procurement will ensure that selected cool pavement products have undergone standard tests demonstrating their ability to retain high friction in wet and dry conditions. Most coating products cure quickly, enabling treated lanes to be reopened to traffic the same day, reducing traffic delays. Most products in use today are [MUTCD](#) compliant and don't require changes to lane markings. Cool pavement has also been shown not to cause glare issues for drivers, as the resulting color and reflectivity are comparable to concrete roads. In some products, reflectivity increases are primarily in the near-infrared rather than the visible spectrum. However, even modest increases in reflectance may improve nighttime visibility on roads, reducing street lighting costs.

7. References

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8. Appendix: Cool Pavements Methods Overview for BCAT1.0

Overview

The Smart Surfaces Benefit-Cost Analysis Tool (BCAT) models the lifecycle costs and benefits of cool pavement coatings applied to roads and parking lots. These estimates are based on the [Smart Surfaces applicability matrix](#) and reflect user-defined percentage-based surface area targets. Annualized costs and benefits are expressed in \$/ft², based on the total surface area retrofitted with cool pavement coatings over the analysis period.

Cool pavement is assumed to be applicable to all land surface areas classified as roads or parking in the LULC dataset, regardless of pavement age, condition, shading, traffic volume, or pedestrian use. The model reflects a high-level planning approach that does not constrain implementation based on site-specific feasibility. Future versions of the tool may refine this approach based on the availability of additional information.

Albedo

The BCAT estimates the solar reflectance (SR) gains from cool pavement applications by comparing the baseline average albedo of roads and parking lots to a target aged albedo value of **0.25**, representing the expected long-term performance of reflective coatings and surface treatments.

Target aged albedo values are based on a review of industry guidance and published field studies across geographic areas in the United States documenting the real-world performance of cool pavement technologies over time. These sources account for factors such as surface degradation, soiling, and local maintenance practices that affect reflectivity persistence.

For each geographic area, baseline albedo values are calculated using zonal statistics, and the **albedo delta**—the difference between baseline and target aged SR—is used to estimate cooling, emissions, and pollution-reduction benefits. This albedo delta is assumed to remain constant over time, reflecting typical maintenance and reapplication cycles based on service lifespans. The model does not simulate degradation or variation in albedo performance beyond what is reflected in these conservative, field-informed assumptions.

Surface Area Estimation

Data for road and parking lot surface areas are sourced from the WRI OpenUrban Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) dataset.

Parking lots are identified using explicit vector polygon and multipolygon features from OpenStreetMap (OSM), which are then validated and classified through WRI's land cover processing methodology. Road surface areas are derived from OSM road centerline geometries, which are converted into polygons by buffering each centerline based on the number of lanes.

For each road segment, the average number of lanes per highway class was calculated using available OSM attributes. Where lane data was missing, the ceiling of the class average was used as a conservative proxy. Road polygons were then generated using a buffer width equal to the number of lanes multiplied by 3.048 meters (10 feet)—the typical average lane width in U.S. urban settings ([Source: NACTO](#)).

This approach provides a standardized and scalable method for estimating the total surface area of roads and parking infrastructure across cities, which serves as the basis for determining the technical potential for cool pavement application.

Product Selection

The BCAT models cool pavement retrofits using generic surface treatments that reflect common industry practices and are applicable to large-scale deployment scenarios. These assumptions are not tied to proprietary products but represent typical material types used for reflective paving. Cool pavement is assumed to be comparable to a high-solar-reflectance (SR) slurry seal. For parking lots, a slightly longer life expectancy is assumed, due to slower traffic.

These product categories were selected based on their alignment with real-world use cases, compatibility with existing infrastructure, and documented performance in independent field studies. Surface-specific assumptions reflect differences in application techniques, traffic load, and expected service life.

Benefit-Cost Analysis Assumptions

Treatment type	Baseline surface	Application cycle (years)	Installation cost (\$/ft ²) [2024 USD]	Sources (application cycle, installation cost)
High SR slurry seal	Parking	7	\$0.78	Industry guidance, Los Angeles Department of Public Works StreetsLA RFP 2022
High SR slurry seal	Road	6	\$0.78	Industry guidance, Los Angeles Department of Public Works StreetsLA RFP 2022
Conventional asphalt slurry seal, type II	Parking	5	\$0.35	Industry guidance, RS Means 2024
Conventional asphalt slurry seal, type II	Road	4	\$0.34	Minnesota DOT 2000, RSMeans 2024
Mill and Repaving (M&R)	Road	15-23	\$2.72	Industry guidance, Ibid.
Mill and Repaving (M&R)	Parking	15-23	\$2.90	Industry guidance, Ibid.
Crack sealing	Road	3–5	\$0.11	Littleton, CO DPW 2025, Ibid.
Crack sealing	Parking	3–5	\$0.11	Littleton, CO DPW 2025, Ibid.

Note: Conventional road service life is assumed to be 15 years, after which milling and repaving are required. Cool pavement road service life is assumed to be 21 years. Conventional parking service life is assumed to be 18 years, after which milling and repaving is required. Cool pavement parking service life is assumed to be 24 years.

First Cost

This is the cost premium of applying a cool pavement coating compared to a typical pavement coating. In the model, the baseline is a slurry seal for cities that regularly use pavement protection.

Note: Some cities have very inexpensive mill & repave cycles and do not use slurry seals at all. This is reflected in city-specific cost-benefit analyses.

Additional Replacements

This category includes the cost of future reapplications of the cool pavement coating as well as crack sealing.

Operations & Maintenance (O&M)

Currently, there are no assumed ongoing O&M costs for cool pavements (i.e., cleaning activities specifically to maintain the reflectance properties or integrity of the coating). If a project included additional street or pavement cleaning, those specific costs would be included.

Avoided Conventional Infrastructure Costs

This category accounts for conventional pavement maintenance activities such as the application of slurry seals and crack seals that would have typically occurred but are otherwise avoided with cool pavement treatments.

Timeline Assumptions

Conventional service lifespans as well as cool pavement application and maintenance cycles were determined based on SSC research and guidance from industry experts and municipal transportation practitioners.

Note: The BCAT’s 35-year analysis window may not fully capture long-term maintenance savings from cool pavement. For example, mill and repaving avoided in year 37 falls outside the modeled period and is therefore excluded from the benefit-cost results. This creates a bias tied to the chosen timeframe: while cool pavement coatings extend roadway service life, some of those benefits occur beyond the analysis horizon. As such, cost-effectiveness results should be interpreted as planning-level estimates rather than full lifecycle assessments.

Surface Life Extension Benefit

Cool pavement applications delay the need for costly milling and repaving by extending the life of the asphalt’s top layer. This deferred cost is accounted for in the BCAT as a lifecycle benefit, resulting in a lower net present value of long-term infrastructure investment. The surface life extension of cool pavements is 6 years for both roads and parking. This benefit quantifies the change in present value resulting from delaying scheduled costs to future years.

Temperature Reduction Modeling

Temperature-related benefits from cool pavement implementation—such as indirect energy savings, avoided greenhouse gas emissions, pollution removal, and health improvements—are modeled using high-resolution hourly micrometeorological simulations conducted by [Altostratus, Inc.](#) These simulations quantify the potential for ambient air temperature reductions from widespread deployment of cool pavement technologies across urban environments.

For each city, Altostratus modeled an aggressive deployment scenario in which 100% of classified road and parking surfaces were retrofitted with cool pavement coatings. This scenario used location-specific albedo change potentials generated by WRI, based on baseline land cover data and surface-specific area fractions for model grid cells. The model outputs include hourly temperature differences between the baseline and cool pavement scenarios at spatial resolutions of 250–500 meters, depending on the city modeled.

To translate these outputs into a form usable by the BCAT:

- Hourly model outputs were aggregated to compute average summertime daily maximum air temperature reductions at each modeled location.
- For each surface type (road and parking), simple linear regressions were developed to relate temperature reduction to albedo change (expressed as °F per 0.01 albedo increase).
- These regressions were applied at the city level to quantify city-specific temperature-related benefits for user-defined deployment scenarios based on the amount of cool pavement installed over time.

The regression coefficients used in the BCAT are fixed and not user-adjustable, ensuring consistency in benefit estimation across cities. All downstream temperature-dependent benefits—including reductions in citywide building energy demand, GHG emissions, air pollutant concentrations, and heat-related mortality—are derived from these modeled relationships.

Negative Radiative Forcing

To estimate the CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) emissions impact of increased surface reflectivity, the BCAT draws on established research linking albedo improvements to global cooling benefits. [Akbari et al. \(2012\)](#) estimate that increasing an urban surface's solar reflectance by 0.01 yields a carbon offset of 4.9–12 kg CO₂e per square meter, with the [IPCC Fifth Assessment Report \(2014\)](#) citing a representative value of 7 kg CO₂e/m²/0.01 SR. More recently, [Akbari \(2023\)](#) reports a median value of **2 kg CO₂e/m²** for the U.S., which the BCAT uses as a conservative baseline. Avoided emissions are calculated using this 2 kg CO₂e/m² per 0.01 albedo increase, converted to metric tons of CO₂e/ft². This value is then multiplied by the [Social Cost of Carbon](#) to estimate the monetary benefit of reduced radiative forcing.

These benefits are modeled as one-time offsets in the year of implementation for each increment of cool surface area. As smart surfaces are gradually deployed over the analysis period, offsets accumulate year by year, but are not double-counted. Reflectance gains are assumed to be maintained through standard surface maintenance, cleaning, and reapplication in line with lifecycle assumptions.

For additional data descriptions, please refer to the [BCAT1.0 Data Dictionary](#).

